

TEACHING ENGLISH IN BLENDED LEARNING MODALITIES: ITS RELATION TO THE STUDENTS' COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCE

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Teaching English in Blended Learning Modalities: Its Relation to the Students' Communicative Competence

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Abstract

In today's rapidly advancing technological world, leveraging these innovations to enhance education is crucial. Blended learning, which combines traditional and technology-driven teaching methods, provides greater flexibility and enriches the teaching-learning process. In English Language Teaching (ELT), blended learning has gained widespread popularity, leading to numerous studies on its effectiveness. This research explores the relationship between teaching English through blended learning modalities and students' communicative competence in selected private secondary schools across three municipalities in Maguindanao: Sultan Kudarat, Parang, and Datu Odin Sinsuat. Specifically, it examines how three blended learning modalities—modular distance learning, online distance learning, and TV-based instruction—impact students' oral and written communicative competence. The results showed that modular distance learning was highly evident, with a mean score of 4.67, followed by online distance learning, also highly evident, with a mean of 4.52, and TV-based instruction was evident, with a mean of 4.25. In terms of communicative competence, oral competence was evident with a mean of 4.35, while written competence had a slightly higher mean of 4.44. Pearson product-moment correlation analysis revealed significant positive correlations between all three blended learning modalities and overall communicative competence: modular distance learning ($r = .575$, $p = .000$), online distance learning ($r = .703$, $p = .000$), and TV-based instruction ($r = .744$, $p = .000$). These findings indicate that higher levels of teaching English through blended learning modalities are strongly associated with improved student communicative competence.

Keywords: *blended learning, teaching English, students' communicative competence, Secondary Public School*

Introduction

Blended learning represents the shift from traditional to innovative teaching techniques, utilizing technology to enhance educational flexibility and effectiveness. In a world of rapid technological advancement, it is essential to harness these tools for educational objectives. However, significant challenges remain that must be addressed to improve the efficacy of blended learning.

Blended learning combines face-to-face instruction with online learning. According to Simpson (2016), many universities are adopting this approach to teach English, aiming to meet the diverse needs of language learners and educational institutions. Despite its growing popularity, several issues still hinder the effectiveness of blended learning, particularly in the context of developing students' communicative competence.

The term "blended learning" has been defined in various ways over the past 30 years. Initially emerging in the business sector, it gained traction in education due to increased computer accessibility and dissatisfaction with online learning's shortcomings (Sharma, 2010; Hong & Samimy, 2010; McDonald, 2008). This approach responds to educational trends by integrating multiple teaching methods.

In English Language Teaching (ELT), blended learning is increasingly prominent, leading to numerous studies examining its different aspects. These studies typically fall into two categories: comparison studies, which assess outcomes from face-to-face versus blended courses, and non-comparison studies that focus solely on the design and implementation of blended courses, along with the attitudes of teachers and students (Grgurovic, 2010).

Tomlinson and Whittaker (2013) edited a volume featuring 20 case studies of blended learning programs across various contexts, including teacher development, English for Academic Purposes (EAP), English for Specific Purposes (ESP), and general English. Their analysis highlights that while blended learning can be highly effective, successful implementation requires careful planning and consideration of how to blend different instructional media effectively.

One of the significant benefits of blended learning is the promotion of learner independence. Students often work autonomously, make informed decisions, and seek solutions to achieve their learning goals. This process helps them evaluate the credibility of online resources, manage their time, and meet deadlines, ultimately preparing them for lifelong learning. However, authors, instructors, and students in blended courses may encounter various challenges that affect course effectiveness.

In the context of the Philippines, Alvarez (2020) identifies blended learning as a relatively new concept. Despite a growing demand, there are notable challenges in emerging higher education institutions that impede effective teaching and learning.

A primary concern is the lack of proper IT training for instructors. To adapt course content in line with evolving technology, educators must stay updated with recent advancements. Institutions must provide opportunities for training, including workshops, webinars, and individual consultations, to help lecturers enhance their pedagogical and technological skills. Continued professional development is

vital, as educators may require time to acclimate to new technologies.

Additionally, the increased workload for instructors poses a significant challenge in blended learning environments. Teachers who transition to online tutoring must dedicate more time to student engagement while balancing their dual roles as face-to-face instructors and online tutors. While this familiarity with students' needs can enhance course organization, it also places additional responsibilities on educators. They must not only exhibit strong instructional skills but also provide content beyond traditional textbooks and facilitate meaningful interactions in both face-to-face and online settings.

Despite the documented benefits and challenges of blended learning, there remains a notable gap in understanding its specific impact on students' communicative competence, particularly within the Philippine context. This study, "Teaching English in Blended Learning Modalities: Its Relation to Students' Communicative Competence," aims to fill this gap by exploring how blended learning modalities influence students' ability to communicate effectively in English. By addressing this research gap, the study seeks to contribute valuable insights into the effective implementation of blended learning in higher education.

Research Questions

The main goal of this study was to determine the relationship between teaching English in blended learning modalities and students' communicative development. Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. To what extent is the level of teaching English in the Blended Learning Modalities in terms of:
 - 1.1. modular distance learning;
 - 1.2. online distance learning; and
 - 1.3. tv-based instruction?
2. To what extent is the level of students' communicative competence in terms of:
 - 2.1. oral communicative competence; and
 - 2.2. written communicative competence?
3. Is there a significant relationship between Teaching English in Blended Learning Modalities and the Students' Communicative competence?

Literature Review

Introduction to Blended Learning

Blended learning, an instructional method that integrates traditional face-to-face teaching with online learning, has gained considerable momentum in recent years. This model offers flexibility, catering to diverse learning styles and contexts. The blending of synchronous (real-time) activities, such as live lectures and discussions, with asynchronous (self-paced) activities, such as online exercises and quizzes, allows students to learn in a more personalized and flexible manner.

The need for adaptable learning solutions has become more pressing, particularly in light of recent global events such as the COVID-19 pandemic, which forced educational institutions to pivot rapidly to online and blended models. As more schools, universities, and training programs adopt blended learning, the focus has shifted to understanding how this model can optimize student engagement and outcomes while accommodating technological and social changes.

According to Garrison and Vaughan (2008), blended learning fosters increased interaction between students and instructors, enhancing both the learning experience and educational outcomes. The mix of delivery methods allows for greater flexibility, making education more accessible, especially in contexts where in-person attendance is not always possible. This adaptability is particularly beneficial in higher education, corporate training, and adult learning environments, where students may have to balance their studies with work or family commitments. The success of blended learning depends on its thoughtful integration of instructional strategies, technology, and learner support systems.

Defining Blended Learning

Despite its widespread adoption, the term "blended learning" lacks a single, universally accepted definition. Different scholars have defined it in ways that reflect its application across various educational contexts. The earliest uses of the term, particularly in language education, described a method that combined online and face-to-face elements. Sharma and Barrett (2007), pioneers in the discussion of blended learning in the context of English Language Teaching (ELT), viewed it as a way to supplement classroom instruction with online resources, allowing for greater flexibility and engagement.

More recent definitions of blended learning aim to provide clarity on its structure and application. Whittaker (2014) and Hockly (2018) emphasize the integration of synchronous and asynchronous learning activities, arguing that the key to blended learning lies in its ability to balance both modes effectively. This balance allows for greater flexibility without sacrificing the personal interaction that face-to-face teaching provides.

"A teaching approach that merges traditional in-person instruction with digital learning methods, incorporating both synchronous (real-time) and asynchronous (self-paced) activities to create a flexible yet structured learning environment."

This definition aligns with a growing consensus in the field, particularly in contexts such as language teaching, where blended learning offers opportunities for students to practice their skills both inside and outside the classroom.

Blended Learning in English Language Teaching (ELT)

The field of English Language Teaching (ELT) has been a significant beneficiary of blended learning approaches, particularly since the publication of Sharma and Barrett's influential work in 2007. Blended learning in ELT refers to the use of digital and online tools to complement in-person language instruction. For example, language instructors may integrate online exercises, multimedia content, and interactive platforms into their teaching. This approach allows students to practice language skills outside of the classroom while benefiting from in-person instruction tailored to their individual needs.

Hockly (2018) notes that the strength of blended learning in ELT lies in its ability to provide a rich variety of learning activities. These activities range from traditional grammar exercises to more interactive forms of language practice, such as virtual conversations and role-plays. Students benefit from both the direct feedback provided in face-to-face instruction and the flexibility of asynchronous online exercises, which they can complete at their own pace.

A significant advantage of blended learning in language education is its capacity to accommodate different learning preferences. Some students may prefer the structured environment of a classroom, where they can engage directly with their teacher and peers, while others may thrive in the self-paced environment offered by online exercises. The blended approach provides a compromise, allowing teachers to cater to diverse student needs while maintaining a high level of engagement.

Additionally, recent research has demonstrated that blended learning can lead to improved learning outcomes in ELT. According to Poon (2013), students engaged in blended learning programs often demonstrate higher levels of language proficiency compared to those in traditional classroom settings. This is because blended learning allows for more time on task, with students able to review material and complete additional exercises outside of class time. Furthermore, the use of multimedia content and interactive tools enhances the learning experience, making it more engaging and dynamic.

Technological Components of Blended Learning

The success of blended learning hinges on the thoughtful integration of technology into the educational process. Blended learning environments are characterized by the use of various technological tools, such as virtual learning environments (VLEs), video conferencing software, discussion forums, and multimedia content. These tools enable instructors to deliver content in diverse formats, providing opportunities for students to engage with material in ways that suit their learning preferences.

White (2014) highlights that one of the key challenges of fully online learning—student disengagement due to lack of personal interaction—can be mitigated by blended learning's combination of online tools and face-to-face components. Virtual Learning Environments (VLEs) such as Moodle and Blackboard are commonly used in blended learning setups, allowing students to access course materials, participate in discussions, submit assignments, and track their progress. These platforms serve as central hubs for learning, where students can interact with both their peers and instructors.

Synchronous tools, such as video conferencing software (e.g., Zoom, Microsoft Teams), play a crucial role in maintaining the human interaction aspect of blended learning. These tools allow instructors to hold live classes, discussions, and Q&A sessions, providing students with opportunities to ask questions and engage in real-time dialogue. Asynchronous tools, on the other hand, such as discussion forums and recorded lectures, allow students to engage with the content on their own time, giving them the flexibility to review materials and participate in discussions at their own pace.

However, Ventayin (2018) stresses that the successful implementation of these technologies requires both instructors and students to possess a certain level of technological competence. Instructors need to be proficient in using these tools to create effective blended learning environments, while students need guidance in navigating the digital platforms. Effective training and support are essential for ensuring that both parties can maximize the benefits of blended learning technologies.

Blended Learning in Modular and Online Distance Learning

The necessity for modular and online distance learning became evident during the COVID-19 pandemic, as educational institutions around the world were forced to adopt alternative teaching methods due to the closure of physical classrooms. Modular Distance Learning (MDL) is a specific form of blended learning that involves the distribution of self-learning modules (SLMs) to students, often in either print or digital formats. These modules allow students to work through the material at their own pace, providing flexibility and independence in the learning process.

Bagood (2020) highlights that the adoption of MDL during the pandemic was critical in maintaining educational continuity, especially in contexts where online learning was not feasible due to a lack of reliable internet access. Self-learning modules provided a solution for students in rural or low-resource areas, ensuring that they could continue their education despite the challenges posed by the pandemic. These modules were carefully designed to include instructional material, practice exercises, and assessments, allowing students to engage with the content independently.

However, the shift to MDL also presented significant challenges. According to Dangle and Sumaoang (2020), many students and their families struggled to adapt to the new format, particularly due to limited access to technology and a lack of guidance at home. Teachers also faced difficulties, as they were tasked with creating high-quality modules while simultaneously learning to manage online and distance learning environments. Despite these challenges, MDL proved to be an effective stopgap measure during the pandemic, highlighting the importance of flexibility and adaptability in education.

The use of online distance learning, which encompasses a range of digital tools and platforms, was also widely adopted during the pandemic. Distance learning allows for greater flexibility than traditional classroom instruction, enabling students to access course materials and participate in learning activities from anywhere. Online learning platforms such as Google Classroom, Microsoft Teams, and Zoom became essential tools for delivering instruction and maintaining student engagement during the pandemic.

Blended Learning and Student Communicative Competence

One of the key areas where blended learning has shown significant promise is in the development of students' communicative competence, particularly in language education. Communicative competence, as defined by Canale and Swain (1980), refers to the ability to use language effectively in social contexts, encompassing not only grammatical accuracy but also the ability to convey meaning appropriately in different situations.

Blended learning environments provide ample opportunities for students to develop communicative competence through a variety of interactive and collaborative activities. Digital communication tools, such as discussion forums, blogs, wikis, and video conferencing, enable students to engage in real-time or asynchronous communication, allowing them to practice their language skills in both formal and informal settings. This blend of online and in-person communication activities mirrors the real-world use of language, making it an ideal environment for language learners.

Nikolai (2017) emphasizes the role of blended learning in enhancing not only students' linguistic competence but also their sociolinguistic and discourse competencies. Through project-based learning, students are required to collaborate with peers, engage in research, and present their findings. These activities promote the development of critical thinking, problem-solving, and communication skills. Furthermore, the use of digital tools in blended learning environments enables students to receive immediate feedback on their language use, allowing them to reflect on their performance and make improvements in real-time.

Myalkina et al. (2018) found that blended learning significantly improves communicative competence, particularly in project-based settings. When students work collaboratively on projects that require them to gather information, discuss ideas, and present solutions, they develop not only their language skills but also their ability to work as part of a team. This has important implications for both academic and professional contexts, where communication and collaboration are essential skills.

Methodology

Research Design

This study used the descriptive correlational design to describe the teaching English in blended learning modality and students' communicative competence. It also examined the significant relationship of those variables. Therefore, this method was appropriate to this study.

Respondents

The respondents of this study were private English teachers from three municipalities in Maguindanao: Sultan Kudarat, Parang, and Maguindanao. The selection of schools was based on their consistent use of blended learning modalities, including modular distance learning, online distance learning, and TV-based instruction. Six private secondary schools were chosen to participate, with a total population sampling employed. In this case, total population sampling refers to including all English teachers from the selected schools, ensuring that the entire population of English teachers using blended learning was surveyed, rather than a sample.

Table 1.

<i>Private Secondary Schools</i>	<i>No. of Total Teachers</i>	<i>%</i>	<i>No. of Respondents per school</i>
Sultan Kudarat Islamic Academy	38	20	20
Ibn Taimiyah Foundation College	37	20	5
Illana Bay Integrated College	35	19	10
Notre Dame of Parang	45	24	6
The Easter Joy., Inc	5	3	3
Shariff Awliya Academy	27	14	6
Total	187	100	50

Table 1 shows that 50 English teachers from 6 private secondary schools participated in the study. The highest number of participants was from Sultan Kudarat Islamic Academy (20 participants), followed by Illana Bay Integrated College (10 participants). Other schools such as Ibn Taimiyah Foundation College, Notre Dame of Parang, The Easter Joy Inc., and Shariff Awliya Academy had varying numbers of teacher-respondents.

The highest number of participants was from Sultan Kudarat Islamic Academy with 20 participants, while in Illana Bay Intergrated College, 10 teachers participated in the study. On the other hand, 20%, 24% 3% and 14% were from Ibn Taimiyah Foundation College, Notre Dame of Parang, The Easter Joy., Inc , and Shariff Awliya Academy respectively.

Instrument

To gather data, the researcher used a researcher-made questionnaire, which was modified to align with the study objectives. This instrument was then subjected to content validation by a panel of experts. The experts consisted of faculty members from Cotabato State University - Graduate School, specializing in blended learning and language instruction. These experts reviewed the content, clarity, and relevance of the questions to ensure they were appropriate for measuring the intended variables.

The validation process involved a series of meetings where the experts provided feedback on each question. Adjustments were made to improve question wording, structure, and alignment with the research objectives. Once the experts deemed the questionnaire valid, it was piloted with a group of non-respondents (10% of the total population) to test its reliability. The instrument achieved a high reliability score of 0.942, based on Cronbach's Alpha.

The questionnaire for teaching English was a researcher-made which was modified to fit the study and subjected to the validation of the experts. This will focus on modular distance learning, online distance learning, and tv-based instruction. The study sought experts to validate the researcher-made questionnaire to be used. Experts on the topic were requested from the faculty members in Cotabato State University - Graduate School who validated for the content of the questionnaire.

The survey questionnaire underwent a reliability test using a pretest dry run to 10% of the total samples which were not included as respondents of the study. This was treated using alpha cronbach test. Results revealed that the survey questionnaire who has undergone alpha cronbach test was highly reliable with .0942.

Procedure

The researcher first sought permission from the principals of the private secondary schools in Sultan Kudarat, Parang, and Datu Odin Sinsuat. After obtaining approval from the principals, informed consent was explicitly obtained from all teacher-participants prior to the administration of the questionnaire. This ensured that all respondents were fully aware of the study's purpose, their voluntary participation, and their rights to confidentiality.

The researcher personally distributed the questionnaires to the selected schools and made sure to retrieve them to ensure a 100% response rate. Friends, colleagues, and acquaintances assisted the researcher in collecting the questionnaires. All data were then securely processed, ensuring confidentiality throughout the analysis.

Data Analysis

The study utilized the descriptive-correlational method to describe the relationship of the teaching English in blended learning modalities and students' communicative competence. It used Pearson r or Pearson Product-Moment correlation to determine if there exists a significant relationship between independent and dependent variables. It is correlation measure used to determine the extent of relatedness of two variables that are at least of interval level. A correlation of -1.00 or +1.00 indicates a perfect correlation.

Results and Discussion

This section presents the results of the tabulated data and illustrated figures based on the responses taken from the data gathering instrument, including the responses analyzed by the subjects.

The Extent of Teaching English in the Blended Learning Modalities in terms of Modular Distance Learning, Online Distance Learning, and TV-Based Instruction

Table 2 presents the extent of the level of teaching English in blended learning modalities in terms of modular distance learning.

Table 2. *The extent of teaching English in blended learning modalities in terms of modular distance learning N = 50*

	<i>Item</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
1.	The teacher monitors learners' performance and reading skills through phone calls and text messages.	4.40	Evident
2.	The teacher prepares an answer sheet for the learners.	4.82	Highly Evident
3.	The teacher makes a weekly home learning plan anchored on the Most Essential Learning Competencies (MELCs)	4.90	Highly Evident
4.	The teacher checks and retrieves learners' answer sheets.	4.84	Highly Evident
5.	The overall instructional delivery meets students' satisfaction.	4.38	Evident
	Overall Mean	4.67	Highly Evident

Legend: 4.50–5.00, Highly Evident; 3.50–4.49, Evident; 2.50–3.49, Moderately Evident; 1.50–2.49, Less Evident; 1.00–1.49, Least Evident

Table 2 presents the extent of the level of teaching English in blended learning modalities in terms of modular distance learning which revealed that teachers make weekly home planning anchored on the Most Essential Learning Competencies (MELCs), check and

retrieve learners' answer sheets, and prepare an answer sheet for the learners with means of 4.90 as highly evident. This result implies that effective teaching in modular distance learning occurs due to well-designed instructional content and the use of the appropriate teaching routines.

According to Ambayon (2020), Modular instruction is more effective in teaching-learning than traditional teaching methods since it allows students to learn at their own pace. It is an unrestricted self-learning process in which immediate reinforcement, such as commenting on a practice exercise, motivates students and piques their interest. As a result, this training method encourages a more student-centered learning approach.

However, it was found out that teachers agree that overall instructional delivery meets students' satisfaction with 4.38 as agree. It suggests that most of the students in modular distance learning meet their learning satisfaction as reflected by their mean averages.

An overall mean revealed that modular distance learning strongly agrees with a mean of 4.67 as highly evident. This suggests that effective teaching using modular distance learning concurs with well-designed content that aligns with the Most Essential Learning Competencies (MELCs) and the appropriate communication with the students. It suggests that it is more effective in teaching-learning because students know at their own pace with modular distance learning. Thus, it indicates that learners have control of their learning and accept greater responsibility for learning. This contradicts Dangle et al. (2020), the primary issues identified were a lack of school money for module production and distribution, students' struggles with self-study, and parents' lack of awareness regarding academic guidance for their child/children. As a result, there are inherent challenges in using modular distance learning.

Table 3 presents the extent of the level of teaching English in blended learning modalities in terms of online distance learning.

Table 3. *The extent of teaching English in blended learning modalities in terms of online distance learning N = 50*

<i>Item</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
1. Distance learning courses provide learning materials online.	4.56	Highly Evident
2. Students use technology such as teleconferencing.	4.54	Highly Evident
3. Students can access course content beyond the scheduled meeting and interact through online conversation.	4.50	Highly Evident
4. The teacher monitors students' progress from time to time.	4.48	Evident
5. Online distance learning measures achievement and learning outcomes.	4.52	Highly Evident
Overall Mean	4.52	Highly Evident

Legend: 4.50–5.00, Highly Evident; 3.50–4.49, Evident; 2.50–3.49, Moderately Evident; 1.50–2.49, Less Evident; 1.00–1.49, Least Evident

As shown in the table, the distance learning courses that provide learning materials online have the highest mean score of 4.56, which is highly evident that most teachers provide materials online to the students to become convenient and available. This result implies that teachers deliver online learning materials that are easily available and convenient to access to the online learners who have the eagerness to learn.

This result corroborates with the study of Stern (2016) that online courses are an effective form of course delivery unbound by time or geography, allowing for accessibility to training at any time from anywhere.

At the same table, the teacher monitors students' progress from time to time. It has the lowest mean score of 4.48, which is evident that teachers observe their students' progress during online learning instruction. This is similar to the study by Brenda (2015) that progress monitoring can give both parents and teachers can their children more and learn faster. It's helped them teach more effectively and make better decisions about the instruction that worked for the learners.

Online learning has the potential to increase scholarly output significantly. The online distance modality has garnered the overall mean score of 4.52 as Highly Evident This suggests that most teachers use online instruction to deliver quality learning to the students. Furthermore, technology is made available to students. The majority of students can easily comprehend the online instructions provided.

In line with Hussain (2020), the findings of this study reaffirm the efficacy of online learning in addressing the educational needs of learners, particularly in remote areas. However, this study contributes to the broader understanding by highlighting not only the accessibility but also the sustainability of such learning models in fostering deeper engagement, collaboration, and long-term educational outcomes. It demonstrates that online learning modalities can be tailored to various learning styles and pedagogical goals, which can enhance learners' engagement and comprehension.

Table 4 presents the data on the extent of teaching English in blended learning modalities in terms of tv-based instruction.

As shown in the table, TV Instruction incorporating highly technical technology for reinforcement has garnered the highest mean of 4.40 as evident. This result implies that using modern approach such as educational television would help students to learn boost their learning from their teachers.

This study conforms with Madsen et al. (2017) and suggests that TV-based instruction can offer a learning gain in both the subject matter used as a reward and the subject matter intended to reinforce. It implies that utilizing technology helps students strengthen the learning they have learned from their teachers.

Table 4. *The extent of teaching English in blended learning modalities in terms of TV-based instruction N = 50*

<i>Item</i>		<i>Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
1.	TV Instruction incorporates highly technical technology for reinforcement	4.40	Evident
2.	TV Instruction designs interactive content to sustain learners' interest.	4.36	Evident
3.	TV Instruction ensures learners understand the lessons and competencies.	4.30	Evident
4.	TV Instruction provides an avenue to accommodate different learning styles.	4.26	Evident
5.	TV instruction follows a weekly plan anchored on the Most Essential Learning Competencies (MELCs).	4.42	Evident
Overall Mean		4.35	Evident

Legend: 4.50–5.00, Highly Evident; 3.50–4.49, Evident; 2.50–3.49, Moderately Evident; 1.50–2.49, Less Evident; 1.00–1.49, Least Evident

On the other hand, TV Instruction provides an avenue to accommodate different learning styles and has garnered the lowest mean of 4.26 as evident. It suggests that TV-based instruction assists students' different learning styles, such as visual, auditory, reading, and kinesthetic learning. This study is similar to Saltrick (2016) that TV-based instruction provides greater accommodation of diverse learning styles, increases student motivation and enthusiasm, and promotes teacher effectiveness.

In summary, the TV-based instruction has garnered a mean of 4.35, as evident. This suggests that TV-based instruction helps students learn about topics they may not have been exposed to in school by opening their minds to various topics. TV-based instruction reinforces what students learn in modular and online learning and serves as a supplement to English lessons. This is similar to the study by Albert (2015) that television is an excellent way to expose your child to a wide range of topics and help them learn about subjects that they would not be exposed to at school. On the other hand, television can augment what children learn in school and serve as a supplement to teaching youngsters about vital subjects.

The Extent of Students' Communicative Competence in terms of Oral Communicative Competence and Written Communicative Competence

Table 5 presents the data extent of students' communicative competence in terms of oral communicative competence.

Table 5. *The extent of students' communicative competence in terms of oral communicative competence N = 50*

<i>Item</i>		<i>Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
1.	Blended learning enhances communication skills.	4.34	Evident
2.	Blended learning improves students' learning engagement.	4.28	Evident
3.	Blended learning improves students' 2nd language communication.	4.28	Evident
4.	Blended learning improves students' oral proficiency.	4.02	Evident
5.	Blended learning promotes collaborative learning.	4.22	Evident
Overall Mean		4.23	Evident

Legend: 4.50–5.00, Highly Evident; 3.50–4.49, Evident; 2.50–3.49, Moderately Evident; 1.50–2.49, Less Evident; 1.00–1.49, Least Evident

As shown in the table, blended learning enhances communication skills and got the highest mean score of 4.34 and interpreted as evident. This result means that blended learning improves communication skills as they are exposed to the different modalities used by their respective teachers. The findings of this study are consistent with Kashefi (2017), who found that students' communication skills improved after participating in a blended learning course.

Additionally, blended learning improves students' learning engagement and improves students' 2nd language communication, which has garnered the same mean of 4.28 as evident. This suggests that student engagement improves their learning of a second language, English. These findings lend credence to Hamilton's (2018) claim that the blended learning model, when applied to the instruction of a second language, has the potential to provide a new framework for engagement, a new chance to investigate learner perceptions, and the possibility for improved learning outcomes.

Moreover, blended learning promotes collaborative learning and has garnered a mean of 4.22, as evident. This suggests that most students are engaging in learning activities, especially online. They were exposed to the various platforms utilized by their teachers.

The findings of this study, which are in line with those of Han et al. (2021), suggest that productive strategies in blended learning models are likely to improve students' collaborative learning experiences. These strategies include helping students adjust their learning orientations, designing some mandatory collaborative assessment tasks, and configuring the composition of collaborative groups.

Furthermore, Blended learning improves students' oral proficiency and has garnered the lowest mean of 4.02 as evident. It suggests that blended learning affects the improvement of oral proficiency like accuracy and fluency. In addition, the blended learning modality facilitates the encoding of the input process and the actualization of the transition from the object and other regulation to self-regulation. Furthermore, the mixed environment aids in encoding input and realizing the transition from an object- and other-regulation to self-regulation. These findings are similar to those of Teng et al. (2022), who found that the blended learning strategy significantly improved oral correctness and fluency, but not complexity.

An overall mean revealed that the students' communicative competence in terms of oral communication had garnered the mean of 4.23,

as evident. The findings of these results are similar to those of Teng et al. (2022) that students can improve their oral competency and practice speaking in a manner that is simultaneously more engaged and more independent when they participate in blended learning environments. This is a possible solution to the difficulties seen in the classroom when it comes to the instruction of speaking. It implies that blended learning enables students to practice speaking and improve oral competence more interactively and autonomously.

Table 6 presents the data on the extent of the level of students' communicative competence in terms of written communicative competence.

Table 6. *The extent of students' communicative competence in terms of written communicative competence*
N = 50

Item	Mean	Interpretation
1. Blended learning promotes reflective learning.	4.34	Evident
2. Blended learning improves writing content, organization, vocabulary, and language use.	4.38	Evident
3. Blended learning articulates thoughts and ideas clearly and effectively in written forms.	4.40	Evident
4. Blended learning improves written learning skills.	4.54	Highly Evident
5. Blended learning promotes autonomy in writing.	4.54	Highly Evident
Overall Mean	4.44	Evident

Legend: 4.50–5.00, Highly Evident; 3.50–4.49, Evident; 2.50–3.49, Moderately Evident; 1.50–2.49, Less Evident; 1.00–1.49, Least Evident

As shown in the table, blended learning improves written learning skills, promotes autonomy in writing, and got the highest mean of 4.54, as highly evident. This result implies that the blended learning modality has been an effective approach to improving students' writing skills, increasing motivation, and learning how to treat writing as one of the learning skills. This result is consistent with Hassan (2020) that the blended learning strategy helps students develop written communication abilities, self-confidence, and an interest in writing.

On the other hand, blended learning articulates thoughts and ideas clearly and effectively in written forms and has garnered the second-highest mean of 4.38, which describes as evident. It implies that blended learning effectively promotes students' communicative thoughts and ideas. This result conforms with Hasanah (2020) that blended learning gives students more learning options and promotes student accomplishment. It improves student learning by allowing them to explore issues independently.

Additionally, blended learning improves content, organization, vocabulary, and language use in writing and has garnered a mean of 4.38 as evident. It implies that the blended learning model is advantageous in English teaching since it enhances students' writing abilities, which is one of the goals of the classroom. This result corroborates with Al Baitaneh et al. (2019) that blended learning improved learners' English grammar skills. They were highly satisfied and encouraged to learn English using similar approaches in the future. It is concluded that blended learning could teach English grammar effectively in EFL settings.

Nonetheless, blended learning promotes reflective learning and has garnered the lowest mean of 4.38 as evident. It hints that blended learning makes it possible for the students to learn anywhere, anytime, with anyone, and record what they think. This makes timeless a problem. The learner is in charge, and they can ask others to join them in their active reflection.

This result is similar to the study by Wilkes (2021) that blended learning allows learners to think anywhere, anytime, with anybody, and record their thoughts. This lowers the time barrier. Learners can ask others to engage in their active reflection.

An overall mean revealed that the students' communicative competence in terms of written communicative competence had garnered the mean of 4.44, as evident. This finding implies that the Blended learning increased English grammar abilities, and students were satisfied and encouraged to continue using it. It can be used to teach English grammar in teaching flexible modalities.

Relationship Between Teaching English in Blended Learning Modalities and the Students' Communicative Competence

Table 7 presents the results of correlation analysis between teaching English in blended learning modalities and students' communicative competence in the three municipalities in Maguindanao, such as Sultan Kudarat, Parang, and Datu Odin Sinsuat

Table 7. *Correlation Matrix between teaching English in blended learning modalities and its relation to students' communicative competence*

Blended learning modalities	Student's communicative competence					
	Oral communicative competence		Written communicative competence		Overall competence	
	R	Sig	R	Sig	R	Sig
Modular Distance Learning	.515**	.000	.590**	.000	.575**	.000
Online Distance Learning	.673**	.000	.669**	.000	.703**	.000
TV-based Instruction	.734**	.000	.682**	.000	.744**	.000

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

It can be gleaned from the table that the findings revealed a significant relationship between variables. This suggests that teaching English has a bearing on students' communicative competence.

Results showed that out of the teaching English in blended learning modalities: TV-based instruction is significantly correlated with oral communicative competence and written communicative competence indicating Pearson correlation coefficient values of 0.734 and 0.682 or .000. There is a strong relationship between teaching English in blended learning modalities and students' communicative competence.

In general, results showed that the students' communicative competence has a significant correlation with TV-based instruction, as evidenced by the Pearson correlation coefficient value of 0.744 or .000. This means that it gives a full picture of the subject being taught. The lessons in English are easy for the students to understand. They can easily learn a lesson while sitting in the classroom or at home. There is not much need for discipline, reprimand, or tension. Furthermore, the null hypothesis states that there is no significant relationship between teaching English in the blended learning modality and the students' communicative competence was rejected. This implies that the higher the level of teaching English in the blended learning modality, the more or better the students' communicative competence.

This is comparable to a study conducted by Albert (2015), which found that exposing your child to a wide variety of topics and helping them learn about subjects that they would not be exposed to at school are both wonderful benefits of watching television with your child.

A Pearson product-moment correlation coefficient was computed to assess the relationship between teaching English in Blended learning modalities and students' communicative competence. Generally, teaching English in blended learning modalities is highly and directly correlated with the extent of students' communicative competence in terms of modular distance learning and oral communicative competence ($r = .515$), modular distance learning, and written communicative competence ($r = .590$), online distance learning and oral communicative learning ($r = .673$) online distance learning and written communicative competence ($r = .669$), TV-based instruction and written communicative competence (.734) and TV-based instruction and oral communicative competence (.744) whose overall interpretation as significant ($p < .001$).

Teaching English in blended learning modalities such as modular distance learning, online distance learning, and TV-based instruction was highly correlated with the values of Pearson r . It was statistically significant at a .01 level.

Conclusions

Blended learning modalities positively impact communicative competence by combining various instructional approaches that cater to different learning styles and needs. Modular distance learning allows students to work at their own pace, giving them time to reflect on and practice their language skills. The structured nature of modular learning promotes self-discipline and autonomy, which are essential in mastering both oral and written communication skills.

Online distance learning, on the other hand, facilitates interaction and real-time feedback, crucial for developing oral proficiency. The use of technology such as video conferencing encourages students to engage in live conversations, improving their spoken language skills. Additionally, the ability to access learning materials and interact beyond scheduled class times provides students with more opportunities to practice and refine their communicative abilities.

TV-based instruction supports visual and auditory learners, reinforcing language concepts through multimedia presentations. This modality exposes learners to authentic language use in various contexts, which can enhance both their listening comprehension and oral communication.

Despite the positive outcomes observed, this study has certain limitations that may affect the generalizability of its findings. First, the sample size of 50 teachers may not fully represent the broader population, particularly in regions with differing access to technology and educational resources. Second, the study was conducted during a specific period when blended learning was adopted as a necessity due to the pandemic, which may have influenced the students' engagement with these modalities differently than in normal circumstances.

Furthermore, the study focuses on three specific municipalities, which may limit its applicability to other regions with different educational infrastructures. Future studies could benefit from a larger and more diverse sample size and consider a longitudinal approach to determine whether the improvements in communicative competence persist over time or if they vary across different socio-economic and cultural contexts.

Given the findings of this study, the following was recommended:

The Department of Education officials may design a plan that will encourage all the public and private secondary that produce a truly integrated classroom where the needs of all types of learners can be met.

The Bangsamoro Ministry of Basic, Technical, and Higher Education officials should see to it sustaining the programs that DepEd officials to uphold the unique traits of Bangsamoro learners as they engage in flexible learning to accomplish quality education across the autonomous region.

The school administrators should improve the delivery of blended learning modalities to the students to improve their oral proficiency

when learning distantly.

Teachers who teach English and other subjects should utilize blended learning modality, especially during this pandemic, to meet the demands and needs of its learners.

References

- Alvarez, Jr., A. (2020). Learning from the problems and challenges in blended learning: Basis enhancement. *Asian Journal of Distance Education*, 15(2), 112-132.
- Barrot, J. S., Llenares, I. I., & Del Rosario, L. S. (2021). Students' online learning challenges during the pandemic and how they cope with them: The case of the Philippines. *Education and Information Technologies*, 1-18.
- Boquia, A., Mohamad, H., Datu Raffy Ralph Sinsuat Sinsuat, M., Maguid, N., Omar, S., Guiaselon, B., & Guiamal, J. (2022). Experiences of designated teacher as guidance and counselor in secondary school of Maguindanao I Division. *Psychology and Education: A Multidisciplinary Journal*.
- Butukan, H. U., Mohamad, H. A., Bawa, L. S., & Kandong, N. A. (2024). Lived experiences of Teduray English language learners on modular distance learning. *Ignition International Journal for Multidisciplinary Research*, 2(6), 1041-1068. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11633960>
- Daungan, F., Guiabar, M., Ronoco, R., Balahim, A.-J., Mohamad, H., Sinsuat, D.R.R. (2024). Exploring the students' level of satisfaction: The use of fern fiddlehead as an ice cream flavor. *Psychology and Education: A Multidisciplinary Journal*, 24(9), 1024-1036. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13691673>
- Del Mundo-Sales, R. N., Mohamad, H., Sinsuat, D. R. R., Parcon, M., & Labangan, B. (2022). Transitions in tumultuous times: Teachers' experiences with distance learning amidst the COVID-19 pandemic. *Psychology and Education: A Multidisciplinary Journal*, 4(3), 299-315.
- Deyamport, W. (2020, October 23). What assessment looks like in a blended learning environment. *Schoology.com*; Schoology.
- Ferlazzo, L. (2020, August 19). Blended learning in the age of COVID-19 (Opinion). *Education Week*.
- Guiaselon, B., Luyugen-Omar, S., Mohamad, H., Sinsuat, D.R.R., Samson, C., Maidu, N., & Maguid, N. (2022). Mismatch of teachers' qualifications and subjects taught: Effects on students' national achievement test. *Psychology and Education: A Multidisciplinary Journal*, 6(7), 573-590.
- Hockly, N. (2018). Blended learning. *ELT Journal*, 72(1), 97-101.
- Karma, I., Darma, I. K., & Santiana, I. (2021). Blended learning is an educational innovation and solution during the COVID-19 pandemic. *International Research Journal of Engineering, IT & Scientific Research*.
- Kasan, N., Kasan, A., Salindao, N. A., & Mohamad, H. (2022). Secondary science teachers' attitudes and performances correlate with schools' performance during modular distance learning. *Psychology and Education: A Multidisciplinary Journal*, 3(6), 542-550.
- Kenney, J., & Newcombe, E. (2011). Adopting a blended learning approach: Challenges encountered and lessons learned in an action research study. *Journal of Asynchronous Learning Networks*, 15(1), 45-57.
- Kumar, A., Krishnamurthi, R., Bhatia, S., Kaushik, K., Ahuja, N. J., Nayyar, A., & Masud, M. (2021). Blended learning tools and practices: A comprehensive analysis. *IEEE Access*, 9, 85151-85197.
- Larsen, L. J. E. (2012). Teacher and student perspectives on a blended learning intensive English program writing course. *Iowa State University*.
- Larson, R. C., & Murray, E. (2019). Open educational resources for blended learning in high schools: Overcoming impediments in developing countries. *Online Learning*, 12(1).
- Manakan, P., Untong, L., & Mohamad, H., Sinsuat, D.R.R. (2023). English speaking skills: The plight of Maguindanaon students: A phenomenology. *Psychology and Education: A Multidisciplinary Journal*, 8(6), 640-647.
- Mangelen, B. J., Bawa, L. S., Untong, L. P., & Mohamad, H. A. (2023). Maguindanaon love songs as tool and springboard in teaching figurative language for Maguindanaon culture preservation. *Journal of Natural Language and Linguistics*, 1.
- Mateo, J. (n.d.). DepEd seeks more funds for "blended" learning. *Philstar.com*.
- Park, R., Digby, C., & Conroy, A. (n.d.). Blended learning as a tool for human resource development in a global context.
- Powell, A., Rabbitt, B., & Kennedy, K. (n.d.). iNACOL Blended Learning Teacher Competency Framework. Retrieved December 22, 2021.

- Quaranta, J. (2017). Descriptive correlational research: Asthma management by school nurses. *SAGE Research Methods*.
- Singer, F. M., & Stoicescu, D. (2011). Using blended learning as a tool to strengthen teaching competences. *Procedia Computer Science*, 3, 1527-1531.
- Tria, J. Z. (2020). The COVID-19 pandemic through the lens of education in the Philippines: The new normal. *International Journal of Pedagogical Development and Lifelong Learning*, 1(1), ep200.
- Yuen, A. H. (2011). Exploring teaching approaches in blended learning. *Research & Practice in Technology Enhanced Learning*, 6(1).
- Mohamad, H., & Parcon, M. (2022). Unfolding stories of English teachers with multiple ancillary functions in Maguindanao-1 Division: A phenomenological study. *Psychology and Education: A Multidisciplinary Journal*, 2(6), 496-501. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6793527>
- Mohamad, H., Sinsuat, D. R. R., & Kamir, N. (2023). Anxieties of grade 6 pupils and home-based teachers in modular English instruction. *Psychology and Education: A Multidisciplinary Journal*, 7(10), 1-1.
- Omar, R., Mohamad, H., Sinsuat, D. R. R., & Parcon, M. (2022). Oral reading intervention activities: Its influence on the pronunciation skill of Bangsamoro grade 3 English language learners in reading aloud. *Psychology and Education: A Multidisciplinary Journal*, 3(6), 1-1.
- Pulindao, F. L., & Mohamad, H. A. (2023). Learners' view of English language learning through modular approach—a phenomenology. *American Journal of Interdisciplinary Research and Innovation*, 2(4), 20-35.
- Reyes, F. M., Abdulgani, M., Aliuden, M. F., Mantikayan, J., Guiamalon, T., Dilna, S., & Nawal, S. Z. (2022). Event management system with SMS notification for Mindanao People's Care Foundation, Inc. *Psychology and Education: A Multidisciplinary Journal*, 3(7), 600-609.
- Rivas, A., Mohamad, H., Lumabao, B., & Sinsuat, D. R. R. (2022). Vlogging among Filipino youth: A discourse analysis. *Psychology and Education: A Multidisciplinary Journal*, 4(9), 846-854.
- Salah, H., Abdulgani, M., Aliuden, M. F., Mantikayan, J., Guiamalon, T., Dilna, S., & Ferolino, M. F. (2022). Adopting human resource information system (HRIS)-enabled government transformation: Perspective of MBHTE employees. *Psychology and Education: A Multidisciplinary Journal*, 3(7), 610-615.
- Salindao, N.A., Salindao, N., & Mohamad, H., Kasan, N. (2022). Modular distance learning gaps: Relationship between teachers' and students' performances in grade 9 science. *Psychology and Education: A Multidisciplinary Journal*, 3(6), 533-541.
- Sinsuat, D. R. R., Abdulgani, M., Mantikayan, J., & Mohamad, H. (2022). The effectiveness of augmented reality (AR) as a tool of office for Ministry of Basic, Higher, and Technical Education in Bangsamoro Autonomous Region in Muslim Mindanao. *Psychology and Education: A Multidisciplinary Journal*, 3(5), 468-479.
- Ugalingan, T., Bawa, L., Carpisano, R., Akmad, A., Mentato, M., Manakan, P., Sinsuat, D. R. R. R., & Mohamad, H. (2023). Causes and coping strategies of stuttering students in speaking English. *Psychology and Education: A Multidisciplinary Journal*, 8(10), 1206-1232.
- Ules, M., Untong, L., Untong, D., & Mohamad, H. (2022). Cocomelon videos: Its effects on Teduray learners' English language learning. *Psychology and Education: A Multidisciplinary Journal*, 3(5), 480-490.
- Usman, S. M., Abdulgani, M. A., Faheem, M., Aliuden, M., Mantikayan, J. M., Abdulgani, R. A., & Mohamad, H. A. (2022). Inventory and monitoring system on logistic vehicles and passengers loading plan for Office of the Presidential Adviser on the Peace Process (OPAPP). *Psychology and Education: A Multidisciplinary Journal*.
- Zainudin, R., Mohamad, H., & Sinsuat, D. R. R. (2022). Thigmotropism in *Vigna unguiculata* subsp. *sesquipedalis* (commonly known as sitaw). *Psychology and Education: A Multidisciplinary Journal*, 4(6), 581-588.
- Zaniel, Z., Mohamad, H., & Parcon, M. (2023). Grade II learners' early language literacy (ELL) in modular distance learning at Simuay Junction Central Elementary School. *Psychology and Education: A Multidisciplinary Journal*, 7(2), 47-60.

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